

Eshmamadov Akbar Normurodovich

Public Safety University of the Republic of Uzbekistan graduate student

"Green" energy is the backbone of the country's economic security

Abstract: this article highlights the role and importance of the "green" energy sector in ensuring the economic security of the state. The main problem of the economy is the limited economic resources, but the limitless human needs, as a result of the increased demand for energy resources, the need to switch from non-renewable resources to renewable resources, the importance of green energy has been revealed. In addition, the directions of the state policy on green energy are highlighted.

Key words: green energy, green economy, economic security, limited economic resources, economic problem, state policy.

Today, on the initiative of the President, solutions to the problems in the field are being sought. It should be noted that the development of "green" energy and the initial steps in this regard have begun.

Of course, such reforms can be the basis for covering the demand in the field. As the President noted, in the last six years, our population has increased by 12%, and industrial enterprises have increased by 2 times, from 45 thousand to 100 thousand. This is evidence that the demand for electricity has increased by at least 35% and it is increasing year by year.

In the address, the honorable President emphasized the issues that need to be implemented in order to improve the supply of energy resources, and said that for the sustainable development of our economy, 25-30 billion dollars of investment in the energy sector is needed, and this can be achieved only by attracting private investments.

As noted, in the last three years, 8 billion dollars of direct investment has been attracted to the industry. In particular, last week, the competition for the construction of 3 more solar photoelectric power plants with a total capacity of 500 megawatts was completed in Bukhara, Namangan and Khorezm regions.

In fact, since the beginning of this year, 7 power plants with a capacity of 1.5 thousand megawatts have been put into operation. Next year, we will implement 11 large projects of 4.5 thousand megawatts. In particular, solar and wind power plants to be built in Bukhara, Jizzakh, Kashkadarya, Navoi, Samarkand, Fergana, Tashkent regions and the Republic of Karakalpakstan will create an additional 14 billion kilowatts of electricity production. This will increase the amount of electricity supplied to households by 50%.

today, the use of energy resources is also the most important issue. The President focused on the same issue and noted that energy consumption in our economy is 2 times higher than in other countries, and therefore we will accept the National Program for Energy Efficiency Improvement.

Based on this, it should be said that today "green" energy can be a solution to existing problems. It is advisable to use every opportunity for this.

In the Address, the President noted that in the next three years, all state organizations will be instructed to install solar panels and hot water collectors, and due to this, 60 percent of their electricity and gas consumption will be transferred to "green" energy. It can be said that the volume of subsidies allocated for the installation of solar panels in households will be doubled, which is the beginning of the work that has started in this regard.

In short, energy is the most important system for the economy of our country. Considering the development of "green" energy as an important factor of the "green" economy, not only system employees, but also residents and consumers are responsible for contributing to it. This is

important in ensuring more effective implementation of priority tasks defined in the Address of President Shavkat Mirziyoyev.

Today, humanity is facing new threats. The population of our planet continues to increase, and the stock of natural resources is constantly decreasing. First of all, we are observing the aggravation of global environmental problems. The world community emphasizes the need to introduce the principles of "green development" in the world economy in order to correct the situation. This approach is reflected in the UN Sustainable Development Goals.

The tragedy of the island is of urgent importance for Central Asia and the whole world, as well as inefficient use of land and water resources,

and environmental problems such as the degradation of the ecosystem, the reduction of biological diversity, the gene pool of plant and animal species, the pollution of atmospheric air and waste water, the accumulation of industrial and household waste, require every country to pay more serious attention to this issue. Such problems are very important for us and cannot be postponed.

Because, if the above environmental issues are not resolved, they may cause irreparable consequences in the future.

The fact that the first direction in the election program of Abdushukur Hamzaev, the candidate for the Presidency of the Republic of Uzbekistan, is devoted to ensuring the country's stable development and accelerating the transition to a "green" economy is a sign of how important and important this goal is.

In order to transition to a "green" economy, the Ecological Party of Uzbekistan sets a number of goals in its election program:

First, a policy aimed at the development of all sectors of the economy based on the principles of "green" economy is implemented. This ensures the rational use of natural resources, their conservation and the restoration of biological resources.

It is known that the transition to a "green" economy in our country is based on geographical location, climate change and innovative approaches. Based on the fact that Uzbekistan has a high technical potential for energy production from renewable sources, first of all, special attention should be paid to the use of solar, wind, small water flows, geothermal and biomass energy in economic sectors, as well as the introduction of advanced innovative technologies in these areas. attention should be paid.

In the election program, it is proposed to create organic mechanisms for the transition to the use of renewable energy sources in all areas of the economy.

Based on the climatic conditions of Uzbekistan, about 97% of "green" energy sources correspond to solar energy. The power of generating solar energy in the regions of our country is from 525 to 760 billion kWh. This is because the number of sunny days per year is 320 days and the number of active sun hours is 3000 hours on average.

Seven years ago, with the initiative of our President Shavkat Mirziyoyev, a new era began in the energy sector in our country. In particular, great attention has been paid to the introduction of renewable energy sources and energy-saving technologies. At that time, some people thought: "This is a temporary campaign." But the past period has shown that they have been renewed. In the following years, a solid legal framework was created for the development of the industry. Foreign investors were attracted and many promising projects were developed. One after another, solar and wind power plants, small hydroelectric power plants are being put into operation. The most important thing is that we are not turning back from the chosen path in this regard. On the contrary, the scope of work is expanding and the pace is accelerating. Last week in the city of Bukhara, under the chairmanship of the President of the Republic of

Uzbekistan, 430 megawatts of renewable energy sources were built in the video selector meeting, where the issue of guaranteeing the population and economic sectors with energy resources was also discussed. They alone produce 1.2 billion kilowatt hours of electricity per year. This means that it is equal to 60% of the annual consumption of social sector objects.

The program envisages support for the widespread introduction of energy, resource-saving and other innovative ecological and digital technologies in the resource-intensive sectors of the economy - energy, construction, agriculture, transport communication system and utilities. By implementing them, first of all, the possibilities of creating material goods to meet the needs of the population and increase their well-being, level of living and quality without harming ecology and the environment will expand.

Secondly, the main producers in the country, especially large enterprises, will be directed to green technologies.

All over the world, including in our country, the rational use of natural resources, their conservation and the restoration of biological resources are becoming more and more important.

One of the main issues before us is the prevention and elimination of problems in the energy system. As we all know, providing the population and economic sectors with continuous energy is a very important issue. From the beginning, special attention is being paid to this in the candidate's election program.

In recent years, 6 new thermal and 1 solar photoelectric power plants have been put into operation in our country, and it should be noted that the volume of new power generation capacity in the last 5 years has exceeded 5,000 megawatts. However, taking into account the growing energy needs of the population and economic sectors, such results may not be enough for our country in the coming years.

In the election program of the candidate, a special emphasis is placed on the development of renewable energy as the safest and most appropriate way to ensure energy stability in the country. In particular, alternative and safe ways to get rid of our people from the problem of electricity shortage in today's modern life are offered by carrying out the work in this regard as quickly as possible and with better quality.

First, we need to develop a "Green Energy Strategy" aimed at the development of renewable energy sources. The important aspect of this is that it will be possible to prevent and eliminate one of the main issues facing us - problems in the energy system.

It is known that a large investment is needed to increase the production capacity of renewable energy sources in Uzbekistan by 15 GW and to increase their share to more than 30% of the total volume of electricity production.

However, judging by today's demand, it is time to take the work to a new level.

Secondly, the widespread introduction of energy, resource-saving and other innovative environmental and digital technologies in the resource-intensive sectors of the economy - energy, construction, agriculture, transport communication system and utilities - should first of all be supported by the state.

Of course, the candidate from the Ecological Party of Uzbekistan emphasizes that the "green economy" does not consist only of reforming the energy sector. Multifaceted measures such as food security, agricultural innovations, sustainable cities, rational waste management, expansion of forest areas, reduction of desertification are also being promoted.

The next step in the transition to a "green" economy is to encourage the population to buy environmentally friendly goods, encourage business entities relying on green technologies, and introduce energy-efficient technologies in construction and energy-intensive industries. When creating this system, the state itself must first of all fulfill its regulatory role.

Another of today's global issues is reducing the amount of toxic gases released into the atmosphere and ensuring environmental safety. Indeed, the main demand of the "green" economy is to develop the general economy without harming nature and the environment.

In the election program of the candidate for the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan from the Ecological Party of Uzbekistan, a number of proposals are put forward that will solve the problem of atmospheric air pollution.

In addition, in 2022, the amount of pollutants released into the atmosphere from vehicles in the city of Tashkent alone amounted to 403 thousand tons, while this figure for the country reached 1 million 296.9 thousand tons. These numbers alone encourage us to think seriously about the future of vehicles running on hydrocarbon raw materials in our country.

Special attention is paid to this problem in the election program. The most important initiative in this regard is to ban the sale and import of passenger cars with internal combustion engines in the country starting from 2030. At the same time, it is necessary to take into account the share of large trucks that cause air pollution, and change the transportation of goods from large trucks to railways and other types of transport that have less impact on the environment.

Such strategic goals are already on the agenda in the developed countries of the world. In particular, in Japan, it is planned to reduce emissions from vehicles to zero percent by 2050 at the expense of renewable energy sources. Great Britain wants to completely ban the sale of diesel and gasoline cars by 2030. In the US, by 2030, it is planned to replace 50% of all new cars and trucks with zero-emission vehicles.

As a result of human activity, 20 billion tons of carbon dioxide gas is released into the atmosphere every year, and more than 300 million tons of plastic waste are created. One of the main principles of the green economy is state support for sustainable production and consumption, as well as the introduction of low-carbon, resource-saving technologies.

The transition to a new economic model requires a step-by-step approach. The main stages of the transition can be seen in the example of environmental initiatives introduced by the European Union.

At the first stage, it is important to reduce investments in environmentally harmful production. Thus, many banks in Europe are stopping lending to gas projects from 2022. This not only deprives the industry of preferential government loans, but also reduces the attraction of private investors.

One of the priorities of our republic is the need for electricity, which is becoming a global issue for all of us, and its rational use, taking measures to introduce cheap, reliable, stable and modern energy.

In order to provide the population with high-quality and continuous energy sources, it is necessary to develop public-private partnerships and attract sustainable investment projects.

Conclusion

In conclusion, our state is taking all measures to support the economic reforms being carried out in our republic and to fully satisfy the population's demand for energy resources. Energy is the most important system for the economy of our country. Considering the development of "green" energy as an important factor of the "green" economy, not only system employees, but also residents and consumers are responsible for contributing to it. This is important in ensuring more effective implementation of priority tasks defined in the Address of President Shavkat Mirziyoyev. An important step in the transition to a "green" economy is to reduce emissions from vehicles. In 2022, the amount of emissions into the atmosphere in Uzbekistan amounted to 2,057 million tons, of which 63 percent came from vehicles and 37 percent from industrial and manufacturing enterprises. That is why we must find a solution to

the problem of vehicles and the toxic gases emitted from them, which have become an integral part of our lives today.

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